

Research Article

Enhancing ESL Learners' Reading Comprehension through the "Main Mystery: Read Between the Lines" Board Game

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Abstract: Many ESL learners face challenges in reading comprehension, particularly in identifying main ideas and making inferences. Traditional instructional methods often rely on repetitive exercises and lack interactivity, leading to low engagement and limited development of critical reading strategies. This study explores the implementation of the 'Main Mystery: Read Between the Lines' board game as a solution to make reading lessons more interactive, student-centered, and effective. The game was designed to help ESL students improve their reading comprehension skills in a fun, collaborative environment. A structured questionnaire using Likert-scale items was administered to evaluate students' perceptions of the game's impact. Descriptive statistical analysis revealed that most learners found the game enjoyable, motivating, and helpful in understanding how to identify main ideas and make inferences. Students also reported increased confidence and enthusiasm for participating in reading activities. The findings suggest that the Main Mystery board game can serve as a practical tool for improving reading engagement and strategy use in ESL classrooms. The study supports the integration of gamified learning materials to create a more meaningful and motivating reading experience for language learners.

Keywords: board game; gamified reading; reading comprehension.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Reading comprehension remains a significant challenge for many ESL learners, particularly in mastering skills such as identifying main ideas and making inferences. Traditional instructional methods, often relying on textbooks and worksheets, may not be sufficient to engage the students or foster the development of critical reading skills and strategies. This lack of engagement can slow down learners' ability to connect meaningfully with texts and to apply effective comprehension techniques. To address this issue, educators are exploring more innovative ways to enhance motivation and active participation in reading activities.

One such approach is the integration of gamification into language instruction. Recent research highlights the positive impact of gamified learning on student engagement. For instance, Liu et al. (2024) found that digital gamification significantly improved EFL learners' language achievement and enjoyment. Additionally, Kaban (2021) reported that gamified e-reading experiences led to higher comprehension levels and more positive reading attitudes among secondary school EFL learners. Hussein et al. (2021) found that incorporating board game activities significantly improved Iraqi EFL preparatory students' reading skills. Similarly, Rizoqulovna (2024) highlighted that board games in ESL classes promote vocabulary building, grammar practice, critical thinking as well as helping to create a dynamic learning environment. In Malaysian context, Mansor et al. (2024) also reported that the use of the Giant Snake and Ladder board game increased engagement and improved English language skills for primary school students. This is further aligned with Zulkarnain's findings that suggests board games transform reading tasks into enjoyable activities, thereby increasing student motivation and participation (2025). Overall, these findings suggest that board games can serve as valuable tools in ESL classrooms, offering interactive and enjoyable learning experiences that can support the development of reading comprehension skills.

The '*Main Mystery: Read between the Lines*' board game is created to meet three specific objectives, which is to make reading practice fun and interactive, to help learners improve main idea and inference skills and also to encourage collaboration, communication, and critical thinking in the classroom.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

The '*Main Mystery: Read Between the Lines*' board game is developed as a hands-on instructional tool to support ESL learners in improving their reading comprehension skills. The main objective of the board game is for players to work collaboratively or competitively to uncover clues and ultimately solve a mystery or crime scene scenario. The game consists of a colourful board featuring paths and spaces categorized into different reading tasks, challenge prompts and penalties. Players draw from a deck of cards that contain short texts or clues accompanied by comprehension questions, particularly focusing on identifying main ideas and making inferences. Players use coloured tokens and a standard die to move around the board. The mystery-solving framework adds an exciting narrative layer that fosters engagement, teamwork and deeper comprehension.

3. FINDINGS

Based on Figure 1, the findings from the study indicate positive responses from the participants regarding the use of the '*Main Mystery: Read between the Lines*' board game in enhancing reading comprehension skills. A significant majority (72.2%) of respondents strongly agreed that the game was engaging and enjoyable, with the remaining 27.8% also agreeing, demonstrating the game's ability to capture learners' interest. In terms of learning outcomes, 77.8% of students strongly believed that the game helped improve their ability to determine the main idea of a text, while 16.7% agreed and only a small minority (5.6%) disagreed. Similarly, 72.2% strongly agreed that the game effectively enhanced their inferencing skills, with the remaining 27.8% in agreement. This indicates that the game was not only enjoyable but also functioned as a purposeful educational tool that targeted essential reading strategies. Additionally, 83.3% of the respondents strongly agreed that the board game provided a meaningful and educational experience, while 16.7% agreed, suggesting that learners found value in the activity beyond mere entertainment. These findings collectively affirm that the '*Main Mystery: Read between the Lines*' board game successfully engages with skill-building, making it a powerful tool for improving ESL learners' reading comprehension in an interactive and motivating way.

Figure 1. Students' perception on the use of 'Main Mystery: Reading between the Lines' board game

4. DISCUSSION

The results of the study highlight the positive impact of using the 'Main Mystery: Read between the Lines' board game as an instructional tool to support ESL learners in developing their reading comprehension skills. Participants reported high levels of engagement and enjoyment, which indicates that the game successfully captured their attention and made the learning experience more dynamic. Beyond engagement, learners also perceived the game as helpful in improving their ability to determine the main idea of a text and to make inferences, which are the two core components of reading comprehension that are often challenging for ESL students. These findings suggest that incorporating game-based strategies in language classrooms can transform reading from a passive activity into an interactive and intellectually stimulating process. The structure of the *Main Mystery: Reading between the Lines* board game, which revolves around solving a fictional mystery through reading tasks and clues, promotes active learning, peer collaboration and strategic thinking. This format encourages learners to process texts more deeply as they are motivated to uncover the answers that contribute to solving the game's overall objective.

5. CONCLUSION

The use of 'Main Mystery: Read between the Lines' board game is significant for ESL educators seeking to create more learner-centered and effective reading environments. By integrating well-designed educational board games into their instruction, teachers can offer learners opportunities to practice comprehension skills in a low-anxiety, supportive setting. Furthermore, the board game format appeals to various learning styles, particularly for students who benefit from visual and kinesthetic approaches. Overall, the implementation of the 'Main Mystery: Read between the Lines' board game highlights the potential of gamified learning to enhance traditional pedagogical approaches and promote more meaningful language learning experiences.

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